

ISic0084

I.Sicily inscription 0084

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

plaque

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Panhormus

Place of origin (modern)

Palermo

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico Regionale Antonino Salinas,
inventory 3537

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 34 cm

Width 45 cm

Depth 7.5 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Hic requiescit in pace
2. Petrus Alexandrinus
3. negotia[n]s linatarius
4. qui vixit an(nos) pl(us) m(inus) LX dep(ositus)
5. sub die XI Kal(endas) Februari
6. as Imp(eratore) d(omi)n(o) n(ostro) Mauricio
7. Tib(erio) p(er)p(etuo) Aug(usto) an(no) XX p(ost) c(onsulatum) eius
8. dem an(no) XVIII ind(ictione) quinta

Apparatus

Text based upon Bivona, ILMusPal (and photograph) with minor typographic corrections

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491827

EDR 137600

EDCS 22100031

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7330 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/books/CILv10pII1883>)

Bivona, L. 1970. Iscrizioni latine lapidarie del Museo di Palermo. *Sikelia*. Palermo. At 37

Agnello, S.L. 1953. Silloge di iscrizioni paleocristiane della Sicilia. Rome. At no.99

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